

Effects of a Structured Yoga Programme on the Emotional and Physical Distress in Hypertension Patients: A Randomized Control Trial

Akhilesh Raizada¹ & Samarjeet Singh²

1. Ph.D. Scholar, Yoga Department, Sam Global University, Bhopal,

Email: akhileshraizada4@gmail.com

2. Research Guide & Associate Professor, Department of Yoga, SAM Global University, Bhopal (M.P.)

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Abstract

The health of the human being is influenced by various factors. Lifestyle pattern can be the cause of origin for a number of health problems which may be physiological or psychosomatic. Hypertension is a global disease but its prevalence varies amongst countries & sub-populations. The prevalence of hypertension increases with growing age & it is estimated that starting from around 15-20% in the early age, it increases to 75-80% in individuals above 70 years of age. Hypertension is a chronic condition of concern due to its role in the causation of CAD, stroke & other vascular complications. It is one of the major risk factors for cardio vascular mortality which accounts for 20-50% of all deaths. With increase in the rate of hypertension a cost effective and easy method should be introduced to control the rising cases of hypertension and to replace the harmful conventional treatments. This work aims at establishing yoga therapy as an accepted and effective system of treatment which can be used by the people suffering from hypertension. The patients selected were hypertensive male and female patients between 40 to 60 years of age residing in Bhopal city.

Keywords: Hypertension, CAD, Lifestyle, Yoga, C.M.I.

Introduction:

Man is making rapid progress in every sphere of life. This progress has increased his access to the facilities which can make his life comfortable while consuming lesser time. But at the same time, this fast lifestyle has also multiplied the stress and stress related issues which are ultimately manifesting at the physical level in the form of psychosomatic problems. Scientists are now able to link a number of health problems with lifestyle. The health of the human being is influenced by various factors. Lifestyle pattern can be the cause of origin for a number of health problems which may be physiological or psychosomatic. One such problem can be Hypertension.¹

Hypertension is a global disease but its prevalence varies amongst countries & sub-populations. The prevalence of hypertension increases with growing age & it is estimated that starting from around 15-20% in the early age, it increases to 75-80% in individuals above 70 years of age. All sections of the population in India suffer & its prevalence in urban population is higher compared to that of the rural population. Hypertension is a chronic condition of concern due to its role in the causation of CAD, stroke & other vascular complications. It is one of the major risk factors for cardio vascular mortality which accounts for 20-50% of all deaths.

High blood pressure (hypertension) means that your blood is pumping with more force than normal through your arteries. There are two types of hypertension. For 95 percent of people with high blood pressure, the cause of their hypertension is unknown. This is called essential, or primary, hypertension. When a cause can be found, the condition is called secondary hypertension.

There is an urgent need to address this disease and search for suitable interventions which can be implemented at community levels. Hypertension is on rise since 1980. The incidence is 20 - 40% in urban & 12 - 17% in rural areas.¹ According to Directorate General of Health Services, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India, the overall prevalence of hypertension in India by 2020 was 159.46/1000 population.² HTN requires the immediate use of medications, lifestyle changes are recommended in conjunction with medication. Because large segments of the hypertensive population are either untreated or inadequately treated, non-pharmacological, alternative therapies with potential BP-lowering effects, such as yoga, deserve research attention.

Over the past 25 years, the resources of health-care services have significantly risen in India and the country has adopted a universal health coverage program. Although the availability of health-care services has risen, the quality of treatment received from different health-care providers is not consistent. Inconsistent guidelines introduce uncertainty in the accuracy of hypertension diagnoses and increase the likelihood of poor health outcomes. Poor health-care literacy, high self-medication rate, poor blood pressure control and inconsistent hypertension management guidelines increase the problem in India.

With increase in the rate of hypertension a cost effective and easy method should be introduced to control the rising cases of hypertension and to replace the harmful conventional treatments. Some researchers have already worked and are working to establish the efficacy of home remedies and exercises in management of hypertension. This work aims at establishing yoga therapy as an accepted and effective system of treatment which can be used by the people suffering from hypertension. One of the main goals of yoga is to achieve tranquility of the mind and create a sense of well-being, feeling of relaxation, improved self-confidence, improved efficiency, increase attentiveness lowered irritability and have an optimistic outlook on life.

Yoga is a holistic healing system that influences all these factors. These factors are Asanas or physical postures, proper breathing in the form of Pranayama or breath regulation, sufficient rest and relaxation through relaxation techniques, expansion of awareness & positive attitude through meditation and optimum nutrition through balanced yogic diet. Thus Yoga is an important natural preventive measure to ensure optimum health through moderation & regulation of lifestyle. Moreover, Yoga is a self-therapy in the sense that one can perform this discipline on one's own.

Hypothesis:

The present study proposed the positive hypotheses which stated that there would be significant impact of yoga on the mental health of mid-aged Hypertensive patients with regards to pretest and posttest or in as a null hypothesis, there would be no significant impact of yoga on the mental health of mid-aged Hypertensive patients with regards to pretest and posttest.

Aims and Objectives:

The study was conceived with the aims and objectives of studying and restoring the mental health of mid aged hypertensive patients considering the current life style and to bring about an awareness among them regarding their mental health. The study aimed at teaching stress management and mental health management through yoga. As a long term goal, the study aimed at teaching yogic practices to increase the will power and self-confidence. To reduce the increased risk of cardio-cerebro-vascular morbidity that are associated with elevated blood pressure.

Methodology:

The patients to observe the comparative effects of yoga on mental health before and after yoga in hypertensive patient were male and female patients with age between 40 to 60 years suffering from Hypertension, selected from clinics and hospitals located in Bhopal city. Out of the initially selected 100 participants (both male and female), 5 respondents either dropped out or were irregular in attending therapy sessions, resulting in a final sample size of 95. The participants were randomly assigned to two groups, namely the Yoga or Experimental group, and the Control group, following the acquisition of their written consent. The Experimental group, consisting of 50 males and females, underwent a structured Yoga program for a duration of 90 days, constituting the treatment regimen whereas the

Control group didn't receive yoga program. However, they were assured of receiving free yoga training after the completion of the experiment. To assess the influence of yoga on hypertension, the Cornell Medical Index (C.M.I.) Health Questionnaire was administered at two distinct points; before commencing the study and after its completion.

The independent variable, that is, yoga program consisted of Asanas, Pranayamas and Relaxation to assess the effects on the dependent variable, that is, Hypertension and Mental Health.

Results:

Data collected before commencement of the structured yoga program and after a period of 90 days was tabulated, cleaned and coded using MS Excel. It was analyzed using standard Data Analysis Tools using the JASP Software, 0.18.3 Version. The normalcy of data was checked using Shapiro-Wilk's test and the results suggest that data has deviated from the normality. Suitable statistical tools were applied to derive the results. Paired sample analysis was carried out to compare values or means between the experimental and control groups. Notably, the data exhibited non-normal distribution. Upon comparing the pre and post data within the experimental group, the p-value was found to be less than 0.001, indicating a significant difference between the two groups. Conversely, in the control group, the p-value exceeded 0.005, our alpha value, suggesting that the significance level was not met, and the data did not demonstrate significance between the pre and post measurements in the control group. The comparisons between the control group and experimental group were conducted to assess the significance of the data. Subsequently, the normality of the data was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test, with deviations from normality verified through JASP software.

Since the deviation from the normality was seen, Mann Whitney U Test had been applied and as a result, the P value deduced is not very significant.

Following tables and graphs are the representation of the results about the descriptives of the data obtained:

	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
Experimental Pre	48	28.958	5.853	0.845	0.202
Experimental Post	48	22.354	6.917	0.998	0.309
Control Pre	47	27.489	7.123	1.039	0.259
Control Post	47	25.574	7.689	1.122	0.301

Table 1: Descriptives

Paired Sample T-Test				
Measure 1	Measure 2	W	z	Df p
Experimental Pre - Experimental Post		760.500	4.711	< .001
Control Pre - Control Post		199.000	2.354	0.010

Table 2: Paired Sample T-Test

This paper is concerned with the possibility of using a simple, relatively well-established, reliable medical questionnaire as a psycho-diagnostic screening device. The questionnaire to be discussed here is the Cornell Medical Index-Health Questionnaire, or C.M.I., as it is usually called. Although a far from perfect psychologic screening device, the C.M.I. could be used both in general and specialty practice to alert the physician to psychologic factors operant in disease processes. The Cornell Medical Index (C.M.I.), a tool designed to collect medical data and standardize patients' medical history, while also incorporating psychological data. The primary purpose is to assist physicians in their initial interviews and help in screening out patients with emotional tensions and anxieties.

The C.M.I. is seen as effective in identifying patients who may require consideration for emotional factors in their overall treatment plan. The passage emphasizes that with proper guidance and practice, physicians can use the C.M.I. to screen out a significant portion of patients with emotional issues. The effects of intervention recorded with the help of this questionnaire were able to deduce the possibility of establishing yoga as a cost effective and safe therapy for hypertensive patients particularly in management of their emotional and physical distress. This is evident by the statistical results obtained as summarized below.

Graph 1: Comparison between Experimental and Control Group

Graph 2: Raincloud plot showing comparison between Experimental and Control Group

On the basis of statistical analysis and subsequent interpretation, it can be concluded that a structured yoga program is effective in management of emotional and physical distress in diagnosed hypertensive patients. These findings definitely pave a way towards establishing Yoga as an integrative therapy for hypertension.

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